

THEORETICAL REVIEW FOR THE INFLUENCING FACTORS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AMONG MUSIC UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 June 2024; **Accepted:** 10 July 2024; **Published:** 30 Aug 2024

Abstract: As the global economy booms, many countries have increased their investment in entrepreneurship education for college students, aiming to improve its quality. However, the trend of international music entrepreneurship research shows that the current situation of music students' entrepreneurship in most countries is not optimistic. China has already opened more than 1,000 art-related majors at colleges and universities, becoming the largest country with art-related professional higher education in the world. As entrepreneurship education continues to progress, people are gradually realizing that relying on college students to start businesses to solve the employment problem is not realistic and is limited by various factors. From the current situation of entrepreneurship education for college students, there are shortcomings in the setting of entrepreneurship courses, the teacher team, the form of course implementation, and the practical teaching model, indicating that China's entrepreneurship education has a relatively late start; at the same time, music-related entrepreneurship education has not been widely promoted in art colleges and universities. Based on the overall entrepreneurship situation and the characteristics of demand for college students, combined with the root causes analysis, the current situation of music entrepreneurship for students of different genders, grades, and types of colleges and universities is studied. According to the research, most music majors have the intention of starting a business, but they lack entrepreneurial ability and practical conditions.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Intention, Motivation, Entrepreneurial Education, Music College Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

In practice, the term “music entrepreneurship” is an umbrella term covering a wide array of

topics and professional behaviors at the intersection of music and entrepreneurship including arts leadership, audience development, career skills for musicians, business training for musicians, navigating the music industry, developing and sustaining a portfolio career as a musician, and the ability to identify and capitalize on entrepreneurial opportunities within the music profession (Brown,2019).

The United States has played a leading role in advancing entrepreneurial education through

numerous successful initiatives that serve as exemplary models for other nations' innovation and entrepreneurial educational systems (Yao, 2019). By 2019, approximately 168 institutions across America offered an impressive total of 372 courses focused on arts-based entrepreneurial studies (Toscher, 2019). Japan's robust entrepreneurial educational framework establishes a strong basis for student development while preparing them effectively for future societal integration. As an influential figure within global educational systems, Europe places significant emphasis on nurturing young children's practical skills and independent critical thinking from an early age; Parents provide less protection, while schools prioritize fostering students' autonomous problem-solving skills (Li and Dong, 2023). In China, the Communist Party's 19th Central Committee meeting emphasized 'innovation as central driver force behind China's comprehensive modernization' and 'establishing high-quality educational systems', aligning with 'National Measures Management College Students' Innovation Entrepreneurship Training Programs' (Jiao Gaohuan[2019],no.13). Additionally, the General Office Sichuan Provincial People's Government introduced various supportive programs aimed at fostering college student entrepreneurs such as 'Opinions Further Supporting College Students' Innovation Entrepreneurship' (Chuan Banfa[2022],75), consistently enforcing guidelines outlined by 'Implementation Opinions State Council Office Deepening Reform Innovation Entrepreneurship Education Colleges Universities' (Guo Banfa[2015],36) to further advance reforms within higher-education-level innovative entrepreneurships, guiding students toward activities aligned with national strategic objectives, and intensifying efforts to foster impactful innovations within key sectors.

In China, the training programs for traditional music majors are tailored to specific areas of study (Li, 2022). For instance, artistic practice emphasizes the development of students' comprehensive musical skills. However, given the current landscape for music major students, the conventional training approach no longer adequately prepares them to meet society's increasing demand for talent (Lei, 2020). As China's education system undergoes deep reform and local colleges and universities expand their enrollment capacities, the number of music majors continues to rise while employment pressures mount. Traditional career paths are increasingly unable to satisfy market demands, leading some college graduates to face unemployment. In response to challenging job prospects in this "difficult employment" environment, many students opt to start their own businesses (Shi and Chen, 2022). Internationally, in light of the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on musicians' activities in 2020 and beyond, there is a growing need for additional knowledge in areas such as marketing, fundraising, audience development and technology. As face-to-face engagements rapidly decline during this period, technical skills become even more crucial for musicians and private tutors (Johnson-Helms, 2023). It is evident that entrepreneurship education in music plays a critical role in cultivating talents that align with current societal needs and international standards; thus making it a focal point of higher education reform efforts (Hu, 2022). Extensive research both domestically and internationally provides compelling evidence supporting the importance of entrepreneurship within music education. The majority of studies on this topic clearly indicate that self-employed artists must possess entrepreneurial acumen. Therefore it raises questions as to why entrepreneurship is not considered an integral part of global music education (Bjørnø, 2018).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entrepreneurial Education Support

In the initial exploration of literature pertaining to music education, it was observed that specific themes within this domain were not as extensively represented in both domestic and international sources as initially anticipated. Consequently, literature related to art entrepreneurship and education, which can be considered a broader concept within the field

of music, was included in the structured search. Certain niche peer-reviewed journals focusing on this subject were not encompassed in either of the two databases. Subsequently, further screening was conducted based on articles' emphasis on entrepreneurship, motivation, intent, and advanced music/art education skills.

Previous studies have explored the influencing factors of entrepreneurial intentions among college students (Abbasiachavari and Moritz, 2021; Gao and Qin, 2022; (Ma and Han, 2023).(Bu, 2018) Through the collation and analysis of the survey data, there are many factors affecting the entrepreneurship of art college students, including three aspects: individual, education support and social support, College students majoring in music are also the same. (Pulka et al. ,2015 ; Guo ,2018 ; Hu ,2022) have focused on music entrepreneurship education, believing that music entrepreneurship education should enhance students' interdisciplinary knowledge to better adapt to the constant changes in social development. Furthermore, they argue that entrepreneurship education helps cultivate students' acquisition of entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors. Art students generally believe that their primary entrepreneurial advantage lies in outstanding interpersonal communication and verbal expression skills, as well as greater creativity and innovative awareness. Yan et al. (2018) indicates that art students are positively inclined towards the in-depth development of entrepreneurial education with targeted and timely content, and express strong entrepreneurial intentions and advantages. However, as of now, the existing entrepreneurship education has yet to meet the needs of these students.

Mantie (2017) study highlights the development of students' artistic entrepreneurial thinking, with the results showing that the projects undertaken by students reflect the values of community development and artistic entrepreneurship and go beyond strict economic factors. We believe that the effectiveness of artistic entrepreneurship education (AEE) programs is directly related to their ability to address and meet the professional and academic needs of students.

Wu and Wu (2008) it is believed that entrepreneurship education should focus on entrepreneurial skills and stimulate students' interest in entrepreneurship, thus making them more likely to conduct entrepreneurial activities. Hutahun (2018) entrepreneurship course and practical training are two aspects of entrepreneurship education that are equally important for the formation of entrepreneurial intention. Valdez-Huaraz et al. (2023) one important factor influencing college students' entrepreneurial intentions is the ability of teachers to create and disseminate knowledge. The survey results also show that students with an entrepreneurial background are more likely to engage in self-employment. Hou et al. (2019) in today's society, with economic development and technological advancements, an increasing number of college students are paying attention to and actively participating in entrepreneurial activities . At the same time, higher education plays a crucial role in supporting student entrepreneurship. Astuty et al. (2022) argue that student entrepreneurship activities can serve as a driving force for young entrepreneurs to rise. Therefore, universities are actively striving to provide students with the necessary entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to build a robust and comprehensive university entrepreneurial ecosystem. Lu and Song (2021) According to the research findings, in a good university entrepreneurial environment, students will be more likely to be inspired and motivated to actively engage in enterprise innovation activities. This positive and affirming environment not only includes hard facilities such as educational resources and research facilities, but also covers soft factors such as mentor guidance and peer exchange. By providing comprehensive support and encouragement, universities can effectively cultivate more outstanding graduates with innovative spirit and practical ability, and lay a solid foundation for their future career development.

2.2 Social Support

Wills (1985, 1991) social support refers to people perception and actuality, that they are valued, cared for and are part of a supportive social network; moreover, they can get support from their social network whenever they need it. In this regard, Langford et al. (1997) suggest that, the presence of social support gives a sense of secure feeling which helps people in making better decisions and leading a stress-less life. According to Uchino (2004) and Wills (1991), SS can be classified and measured using four different dimensions. They believe that the four dimensions are: emotional support, tangible support, informational support, and companionship support. Emotional support. Emotional support is an intangible form of support received from one's social network (Farooq, 2016). Tangible support. A recent study by Farooq (2016) has revealed that every year more than 50 per cent nascent entrepreneurs dump their business ideas, due to lack of resources and finance required for a new business venture. Informational support. Success of new business ventures is highly dependent on correct and timely decisions made by their founders, and correct decisions are not possible without having correct information or prior work experience (Farooq, 2016). Companionship support. Business is a social activity, which is not possible in isolation (Kolvereid and Isaksen, 2006; Miralles et al., 2015;

Semrau and Werner, 2014).

Jen (2019) and Zhang (2019) conducted research focusing on the supportive factors of entrepreneurial intention in social environments. They found that social environments, including family, friends, teachers, and professionals, have a significant impact on participants' entrepreneurial intentions. In the workplace and the entrepreneurial process, college students often face various challenges and difficulties, and the entrepreneurial process is a showcase of their overall abilities. Ao and Liu (2015) If individuals are deterred from starting a business due to concerns about losing face, or if they lack tolerance for business failure, they may be unwilling to initiate the formation of a new enterprise. When an individual receives support from their family and friends for their entrepreneurial plan, they gain strength and can maintain optimism in the face of challenges. Ismail and Khalid (2009) highlighted the importance of family and friend support in research. (Si et al., 2022; Schwarz, 2009; Neneh, 2022) the level of social support is closely related to the self-affirmation, sense of responsibility, and entrepreneurial spirit of college students who start businesses. With the support of important others, college student entrepreneurs can enhance their sense of responsibility and therefore maintain a strong entrepreneurial intention. Social support perceptions can help college students cope with crises and stressful events, enhancing their ability to adapt to their environment, reducing stress, and decreasing entrepreneurs' withdrawal tendencies.

Hutasuhut (2018) pointed out that the family is one of the direct environments that impact individuals. According to the survey results of Jiang (2021), music major college students receive the most significant external support from their families during the entrepreneurial process. Chen and Yang (2022) found that parents who have entrepreneurial experience and can provide resource support are more likely to encourage college students to choose entrepreneurship. (Hutagalung et al., 2017; Shamsudin and Mamun, 2017). The research results indicate that besides the environmental background, family members play an important role in influencing an individual's behavior and life choices in enhancing their autonomous entrepreneurial intentions. Relying on the emotional, intellectual, and financial support from family members can help young entrepreneurs cultivate the next generation of entrepreneurial spirit, and they can obtain help in the first-hand practice regardless of their personal level of entrepreneurial knowledge. Moreover, individual family members can provide suitable mentors and advisors for children who are considering starting a business. From the perspective of role modeling, the family has an impact on an individual's

entrepreneurial intentions and believes that parents play an important role in a child's entrepreneurial career. Gao and Qin (2022) pointed out that more than 50% of potential entrepreneurs give up their ideals due to a lack of economic support every year. Students with relatively fewer social resources usually rely on initial funding from their families or through loan methods to establish their businesses. Consequently, the poor family economic conditions may weaken the support that could be provided.

2.3 Personal Traits

A set of studies has used the Big Five personality traits (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism) to assess students' EI, which was established by Fiske (1949), but there is insufficient research on the relationship between implicit motives and entrepreneurial intentions. Sahin et al. (2019) pointed out that personality plays an important role in entrepreneurship, however, the findings of previous studies on the relationship between specific personality traits and entrepreneurial intentions have varied. Some scholars conducted a meta-analysis of five studies on entrepreneurial personality and found that the meta-analytic pattern did not fully reflect the five personality traits. Additionally, other scholars' meta-analysis results overlapped but were not entirely consistent. Luc et al. (2022) examined the relationship between the Big Five personality traits (i.e., agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, extraversion, and openness) and social entrepreneurial intentions. The results indicated that individuals with different personality traits exhibit varying levels of social entrepreneurial aspirations. Bazkiaei and Heng (2020) pointed out that personality and attitude combined can positively influence entrepreneurial intentions and improve the entrepreneurial atmosphere of a country to promote economic development. Sahin et al. (2019) believed that open-mindedness and motivation were the core conditions, combined with stable emotions, agreeableness, and extroversion as peripheral conditions, were sufficient to enhance students' high levels of entrepreneurial intentions.

2.4 Entrepreneurial Motivation

Motivation is considered a crucial factor in enhancing students' capabilities. Many studies have adopted the TPB framework proposed by Ajzen (1991), which includes personal attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control as antecedents of entrepreneurial intention. Farooq (2018) found that entrepreneurial skills had a significant positive direct impact on entrepreneurial attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intentions. Confirming the positive correlation between perceived entrepreneurial skills and behavioral control is a crucial link in the confidence needed to create a new business. Having entrepreneurial skills can inspire independence and the desire to become one's own boss.

3. THEORETICAL REVIEWS

This study also explores the relationships between the ecosystem theory, social support network theory, Big Five personality theory, behavioral planning theory, and the entrepreneurial intention of music major college students. By using music entrepreneurial motivation as a mediating factor, this study examines the impact of school educational support factors, social support factors, personal traits, and music entrepreneurial motivation on Chinese college students' entrepreneurial intention.

3.1 Bronfenbrenner's Theory of Ecosystems

Liu et al. (2023) introduced the theory of ecosystems into their study, constructing an ecosystem model for entrepreneurship education in schools to promote the work of entrepreneurship education for college students. The study provided theoretical guidance and practical utility for action plans. To strengthen entrepreneurship education in universities, it

is necessary to start from the micro, meso, external, and macro systems. The educational implementation agency should clarify the boundaries of responsibility, and schools, families, and society should develop and educate together. Government functional departments should guide the work, and society should create a healthy and upward cultural environment. Starting from school social work intervention and based on the theory of social ecosystems, by constructing personal, family, school, and social resources, a holistic entrepreneurship education ecosystem can be built to link local ecological elements and coordinate the operation of various stakeholders. This ecosystem can then serve as the core to support the work of entrepreneurship talent cultivation in universities (Liu, 2023).

Social ecosystem theory was first proposed by Yu Bronfenbrenner. In 1979, he introduced the knowledge of ecology into the study of human behavior and pointed out that the environment has an important impact on individual behavior and psychological development. Charles Zastrow further developed on this basis and expounded the relationship between personal growth and social environment. He divided the social ecosystem into three basic types: micro, meso and macro systems. The so-called micro-system refers to the individual in the social ecological environment; The meso-system refers to small groups related to individuals, such as communities, schools, and companies; Macro system refers to a social system larger than a small group, including cultural organizations or institutions, institutions, and customs. There is interaction between individual and social ecosystem. Individual behavior and environment influence each other, restrict each other and complement each other. Ecosystem theory provides an important theoretical perspective for this study. From the perspective of ecosystem theory, the micro-system of entrepreneurship is mainly students themselves. The meso-system mainly refers to the entrepreneurial environment (educational support) and the social entrepreneurial environment (social support) in the school where the student is located; The macro system mainly refers to the socialist system environment of China and the social system of Sichuan Province.

Figure 2.1: Graphic Depiction of the Bronfenbrenner Model

Source: Mooney (2015)

3.2 Ajzen's theory of planned behavior

Chinese scholars have achieved certain results in the study of college student entrepreneurship by applying the TPB theory (Yang et al., 2023). Li et al. (2008) and Hu(2014) found that the theory of planned behavior can explain college students' entrepreneurial motivation well and reveal that Chinese college students' entrepreneurial intentions mainly come from intrinsic motivation, while emphasizing the influence of

personal personality traits on entrepreneurial intentions.

TPB, first proposed by Ajzen (1991), assumes that most of human behavior is planned. Therefore, TPB believes that individual behavioral intentions and actual behavior are formed by the individual's attitude towards behavior, subjective norms and their perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 2011). In assessment of entrepreneurial behavior, Ajzen (1991) TPB has been applied to many studies. The efficacy of TPB has received considerable attention in various areas of research, particularly in entrepreneurial education. Starting from Ajzen's theory (TPB), proved that both the attitude towards entrepreneurial behavior (PA) and the perceived behavioral control (PBC) have a significant impact on the entrepreneurial intention (EI) of college students (Barba-Sánchez et al., 2023).

Figure 2. 1: Structural model of the planned behavior theory Fig

Source: Duan&Jiang (2008)

Several models of the willingness to start businesses have been developed, including various variables, as well as some pre-entrepreneurial experiences focusing on using attitudes and behavior theory. Among them, the theory of planning behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is the most highly structured, and is fully recognized in Malaysia (Ali et al., 2018). TPB can explain the intention of entrepreneurial activities. (Bazkiaei et al. 2020). Gao and Qin (2022) In order to further promote economic and social development, the Chinese government and universities have launched entrepreneurship education courses to encourage college students to participate in entrepreneurship competitions to improve their entrepreneurial knowledge, ability and willingness. However, the willingness of Chinese college students to start their own businesses is still low. Research developed a theoretical model to explain the mechanisms shaping entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions.

3.3 Social support network theory

Polabay's attachment theory is the fundamental basis for social support, which was first applied to psychiatric clinical treatment in the 1960s. In the 1970s and 1980s, the American social support program promoted the development of social support networks. The basic assumption is that humans cannot exist in isolation, and survival requires cooperation and dependence on others. Individuals form a network of relationships, through which they maintain identity, receive emotional support, receive material assistance, access services, information, and new social contacts. The support system built from various tangible and intangible forms of support constitutes one of the resources required for the life development of social support networks. Individuals form relationship networks through their interactions with others, which help maintain their identity and provide emotional support, material assistance, services, information, and new social contacts. This support system, built from various tangible and intangible forms of support, is known as the social support network. According to the theory of social support network, in this study, social support for entrepreneurship is defined as the non-formal help and support from others, including

informal help from individuals or formal support from relevant organizations, that individuals can enjoy during the entrepreneurial process. Specifically, Based on previous research by Liñán and Chen (2009), that social network support in this study is primarily based on private relationships, including spiritual support and material assistance from individuals around the research subject, such as parents, siblings, relatives, teachers, close friends, etc.

Chen et al.(2024)Based on the theory of social support network, this study aims to investigate the direct impact of family socioeconomic status and social support on college students' entrepreneurial readiness, as well as the specific driving mechanisms. The results show that both family socioeconomic status and social support positively influence college students' entrepreneurial readiness, with informal support being more significant. Furthermore, family socioeconomic status directly promotes college students' entrepreneurial readiness through both formal and informal support channels, with the latter having a more pronounced effect than the former. Therefore, it is crucial to establish a multi-dimensional collaborative mechanism, including social, academic institutions, and family sectors, to enhance entrepreneurial education for promoting employment through entrepreneurship. Liu et al. (2017) and Fu (2016), in the current economic environment, college students starting a business face both challenges and opportunities. They need more comprehensive legal and regulatory frameworks and a more supportive financial services system. Therefore, in promoting college student entrepreneurship, in addition to family and friends, the government, schools, society, and enterprises should work together to build a robust and comprehensive formal social support network and provide more extensive and in-depth assistance and guidance.

3.3 Big Five Personality Theory

The Big Five personality theory, also known as the five-factor model, was developed by American psychologists Paul Costa and Robert Marclay. The development of the theory can be traced back to the 1950s. After years of research and verification, the Big Five personality theory has gradually become one of the mainstream models to describe individual personality traits. It classifies personality traits into five dimensions, They are Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness to Experience, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. The Big Five personality theory provides a powerful framework for understanding and describing individual personality traits, and provides an important theoretical basis for application in various fields. It has been widely used in psychology, human resource management, mental health assessment, personal development and other fields. The Big Five personality theory is used to help individuals understand their own personality characteristics, guide personal growth and career development planning and leadership style prediction

Personality trait theory regards trait as the basic characteristic that determines individual behavior, the basic element of personality, and the basic unit of personality evaluation. G.W., American psychologist Allport believed that traits were the basic elements of personality, the tendency of a person to react in a particular way, based on a person's 'neuropsychological system', which could not be directly observed but could be confirmed by human behavior. There is relative independence between traits. Traits can be possessed either by an individual or by a group." Every trait is the unity of uniqueness and universality. The existing research results show that the differences between individuals can be explained by five personality factors. The most widely used of the general personality trait theories is the Big Five personality theory (Chen and Yang,2022). In this sense, the Big Five personality traits, also known as the five-factor model (FFM), is one of the most comprehensive and highly valued personality trait theories. Based on the theory of Big Five personality model, Tao and Hu(2018)The results show that most successful graduates show high extroversion, agreeableness, openness, conscientiousness and low neuroticism. The conclusion of the

study is that the personality traits of entrepreneurs do have a significant impact on entrepreneurial results, but there is no inevitability. Among the personality traits of entrepreneurial college students, the characteristics that are helpful to successful entrepreneurship can be consciously stimulated and induced through entrepreneurial education, so as to effectively change and improve the effect of entrepreneurial education.

In this study, students' motivation for music entrepreneurship, music entrepreneurial education support, social support, and students' personality traits are considered as relevant factors in addressing the research problem. Specifically, students' musical motivation is treated as an independent and mediating variable rather than exerting direct effects between independent and dependent variables.

4. DISCUSSION

Valdez-Juárez et al. (2023) the study points out that a decisive factor in university entrepreneurial intention is the role of the teacher through his ability to create and spread knowledge. The survey results show that college students with entrepreneurial background are more likely to start their own business. The study contributed to the development of planning behavior theory. Liu et al. (2019) the entrepreneurship education of college students has a significant positive impact on their entrepreneurial intentions, but no significant impact on their entrepreneurial attitude. Secondly, college students' entrepreneurship has a significant positive effect on their entrepreneurial attitude and entrepreneurial intention. Wu et al. (2008) conducted a study using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) model to examine how Chinese college students develop entrepreneurial intentions. The study emphasizes that effective entrepreneurship education should prioritize the development of practical skills required by entrepreneurs, while also stimulating students' enthusiasm for entrepreneurship through structured courses and experiential learning opportunities.

Hong (2021) The study findings suggest that schools should take the initiative to raise funds, fully utilize alumni, parents, and social resources to establish entrepreneurship funds to support the entrepreneurial activities of art majors, and invite successful entrepreneurs to interact with students to help them deeply understand the essence of entrepreneurship and establish the correct entrepreneurial awareness. At the same time, music students need to be supported and encouraged by trustworthy supporters to stimulate their inner motivation. Lu and Song (2021) used a sample of 13,954 Chinese university graduates to investigate students' perceptions of university support and its impact on their intention to start a business. The study showed that entrepreneurial motivation has always been a key factor influencing entrepreneurial intention. The entrepreneurial environment composed of family, school, enterprises, and other entities also has a profound impact on college students' entrepreneurial intentions and performance. Graduates believe that the university's entrepreneurial environment and support system are recognized, which has a significant impact on graduates' entrepreneurial intentions. That is, a good university entrepreneurial environment and support will stimulate students' EI.

Citrawandi & Susanto (2020) employed a quantitative research approach in their investigation involving Indonesian student participants totaling 320 individuals. Their findings revealed that entrepreneurship education as well as course delivery significantly influence student's inclination towards entrepreneurship; additionally, lecturer competence plays a pivotal role in shaping such intent. Chen & Hsiao's (2015) examination in Taiwan utilized internally developed instructional materials alongside industry experts as co-instructors which resulted in heightened satisfaction among learners regarding curriculum structure while concurrently enhancing their practical acumen within the realm of entrepreneurship studies; however, it did not directly translate into increased proclivity for initiating new ventures post-course completion. Thus indicating that effective

entrepreneurship education should encompass both vocational training for pursuing an enterprising career path along with nurturing an enterprising mindset adaptable for future professional endeavors. Ismail et al. (2009) work demonstrated disparities in entrepreneurial aspirations between participants enrolled or unenrolled within dedicated entrepreneurship programs; those engaging directly with entrepreneurs or small business proprietors exhibited heightened enthusiasm potentially attributed to experiential learning garnered from immersive involvement within enterprise-related disciplines.

Ao and Liu (2014) social cognition exerts its influence on an individual's entrepreneurial intention in two ways: perceived social pressure and support and encouragement from family members, relatives, and friends. According to the theory of planned behavior, if potential entrepreneurs receive unsupportive information from family members, friends, or other important individuals, they may lack confidence in their entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, social and family support have a positive impact on an individual's entrepreneurial intention. Social cognition exerts a dual influence on an individual's entrepreneurial aspirations through their perception of social pressure and support from family, relatives, and friends. Consistent with Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behavior, when faced with unsupportive feedback from family members, friends, or other important figures, aspiring entrepreneurs may lack confidence in pursuing their entrepreneurial ventures. Therefore, social and family support have a significant role in enhancing an individual's entrepreneurial intention.

In a study conducted by Neneh (2022), it was found that social support had a positive and statistically significant influence on entrepreneurial intention, based on an analysis of 500 valid responses from college students. Similarly, Khayru and Nichen (2021) observed a direct correlation between the level of social support received by teenagers and their entrepreneurial intentions, indicating a noteworthy and positive association. Farooq (2018) used simple random sampling to collect data from 281 respondents, it was found that social support has a significant impact on individual entrepreneurial intentions, especially those with high social support are more likely to start a business. Moreover, social support is a better predictor of entrepreneurial behavior than subjective norms. Si et al. (2022) discovered a positive correlation between the level of social support received and the affirmation of self, sense of responsibility, and maintenance of entrepreneurial intention among college students. Furthermore, perception of social support was found to facilitate better adaptation to crises and stress events, leading to reduced entrepreneurial retreat psychology. Additionally, active social support was observed to elevate the innovation and achievement levels of college student entrepreneurs. Moreover, demonstrating respect for others' feelings and needs was associated with a firmer affirmation of personal entrepreneurial intention and promotion of entrepreneurial activities among college students.

Israr and Saleem (2018) suggest that families with entrepreneurial occupations can provide young people with opportunities to access certain business skills. Research indicates that families with entrepreneurial occupations can provide young people with access to certain business skills, confidence, experience, and exposure, all of which contribute to their propensity to start a business. Wang et al. (2018) study found that parents perceived entrepreneurial rewards and entrepreneurial intentions, also provide practical guidance for parents as entrepreneurs, clear parents perceived entrepreneurial rewards and family companies involved in the influence of their children's entrepreneurial intentions.

Pruett et al. (2009) conducted a study that surveyed over 1,000 college students from the US, Spain, and China. The results showed that the expectation of family support was significantly related to the participants' willingness to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The study's findings indicate that students who have entrepreneurial family members are more likely to plan to start their own businesses. Not surprisingly, the expectation of family support for entrepreneurship was positively related to the intention to start a business. On the other hand,

students who expected negative reactions from their family were less likely to plan to start a business. However, the cultural values related to the country and the expected family support had a minimal impact on the intention to start a business, while personal characteristic-related variables were more important.

Ali and Alshiqi (2023) explores the views of students in contested regions and proposes a framework for evaluating entrepreneurial mindset in special administrative regions. The results show that personality traits significantly influence students' entrepreneurial intentions in contested areas. Elshar and Sobai (2023) conducted a survey among senior students majoring in agriculture and food science at four public universities in Saudi Arabia. The five major personality traits had a significant positive impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions. Specific personality traits were positively correlated with entrepreneurial intentions, such as agreeableness, conscientiousness, extraversion, and experience openness, while neuroticism was negatively correlated. Tsaknis and Sahinidis (2022) the study found that personality traits have both direct and indirect effects on emotional intelligence, with conscientiousness having a direct negative impact on emotional intelligence.

Bazkiaei and Heng (2020) used quantitative methods to address the research objective, investigating the student entrepreneurial intentions of three research-oriented public universities in Malaysia and collected data from 165 respondents through a questionnaire. The study findings indicate that by studying students' entrepreneurial attitudes, maintaining a connection with their personality traits, and educating them, it is possible to increase entrepreneurial intentions. If the students' personality and attitudes are combined, a positive impact can be made on their entrepreneurial intentions, thereby improving the national entrepreneurial atmosphere and benefiting economic development. Frago et al. (2020) the proposed personality traits and entrepreneurial attitudes serve as robust predictors of college students' intentions to engage in entrepreneurship.

Zhao and Saporta (2006) proposed that personality should be considered a key element in a multidimensional model that covers variables, processes, and environmental factors that influence entrepreneurship and the creation of new businesses. The importance of specific variables, such as personality traits, may vary significantly at different stages of a new project. For example, openness may be critical in the early stage where identifying opportunities is crucial, but high conscientiousness may be critical in the subsequent stage where entrepreneurs focus on providing products or services. Although the potential personality dimensions of the FFM are relatively stable, many behaviors associated with these variables can be cultivated through practice and effort. Individuals with high conscientiousness are more likely to set and stick to goals, which is related to higher job performance. Training aimed at cultivating behaviors relevant to acquiring an entrepreneurial identity may bring great benefits to individuals and societies seeking an entrepreneurial career - this pursuit would be greatly enriched by entrepreneurial activities.

Zhao Dong (2015) validated the factor structure of personality traits impacting entrepreneurial intentions using a sample of 274 ICT students from Taiwan. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial intentions encompass two dimensions—belief and preparation—with openness and conscientiousness exerting positive influences across both dimensions; however extroversion's impact was non-significant for either dimension along with neuroticism's effect being negligible overall except for its negative association with preparedness for entrepreneurship initiation. Furthermore, an interaction effect was observed between openness trait & accountability behavior shaping one's inclination towards entrepreneurship pursuit. Wu and Wang (2016) also showed that personality traits such as openness, conscientiousness, and extroversion have a significant impact on college students' entrepreneurial intentions.

Motivation is widely believed to be a key factor in enhancing students' abilities. This study will investigate entrepreneurial motivation, with a particular focus on attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which are the main factors that influence students' willingness to engage in entrepreneurial activities in the music industry. Gao and Qin (2022) In order to further advance economic and social development, the Chinese government and universities have initiated entrepreneurship education programs aimed at encouraging college students to engage in entrepreneurial competitions with the goal of enhancing their knowledge, skills, and inclination for entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, the propensity of Chinese college students to embark on entrepreneurial ventures remains relatively low. This study employed a quantitative approach to gather 351 sample data points and constructed a theoretical model elucidating the mechanisms that influence entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions. The study empirically validated that the formation of entrepreneurial intentions among Chinese college students is influenced by the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB).

Maheswari (2022) conducted an online survey among 164 students at the Vietnam National University, and the study also found that the TPB elements have a greater impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions. Shi et al. (2020) conducted a study in China that found that cultivating creativity in entrepreneurship education is crucial for stimulating innovation, and that entrepreneurial attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control all have significant positive effects on entrepreneurial intention. Alam and Kousar (2019) aims to expand the Theory of Planning Behaviour (TPB) model by focusing on the intention-action gap, which is considered under researched by academic researchers. It further examines the regulation of entrepreneurial motivation between intention and behavior (action) to improve the predictability of TPB for senior engineering students in Pakistan. Data collection survey was conducted on 448 engineering students from four major engineering universities. The results indicate that attitude and perceived behavioral control are positively associated with entrepreneurial intention, and entrepreneurial motivation significantly affects the intention-behavior association of TPB, which is a new finding of TPB elongation."

5. CONCLUSION

According to Snuggs and Jevons (2018) and Jiang (2021), integrating comprehensive music education programs into entrepreneurial academic institutions is a necessary prerequisite for cultivating well-rounded individuals who can make positive contributions to local communities and global society. Entrepreneurial education is rapidly becoming one of the most dynamic subjects globally, with an increasing number of people interested in combining current business practices with academic theory. The powerful economic impact of combining music art with entrepreneurship highlights its crucial role in nurturing a thriving creative economy. Therefore, the increasing emphasis on entrepreneurial education reflects the growing interest of the education community on this subject. Music majors have a high interest in entrepreneurship, but they have insufficient knowledge of entrepreneurship policies. They hope to enhance their entrepreneurial skills through more practical opportunities and relevant courses, and look forward to support from the government and the school. At school, some music majors have actively participated in various innovation and entrepreneurship activities, including hosting music performances and designing music products, showing a strong desire to start their own business. At the same time, they also aspire to receive more training in marketing, financial management, etc., in order to better plan and develop their music careers. A good social network support and the personal traits (the Big Five personality traits) of college students have a positive impact on their entrepreneurial intentions. In today's society, entrepreneurship has become a career choice that is encouraged and pursued. A good social network support can provide college students with help in resource sharing, information transmission, and emotional support, thus

enhancing their confidence and courage needed in the entrepreneurial process. In addition, personal traits are also one of the important factors that influence the positive impact of entrepreneurial intentions. For example, in the Big Five personality traits, openness, conscientiousness, and extraversion may all have an impact on whether or not a person is willing to take risks and try new things. The motivation to start a music business is considered to be an important driving force for college students to embark on the path of entrepreneurship. This motivation stems from a love for the music industry and confidence in one's own talent, inspiring them to pursue innovation and explore the possibility of commercial success. In the digital age of today, starting a music business is not just about artistic expression, but also a combination of cross-border cooperation and business practices. Therefore, the inspiration and influence that music entrepreneurship possesses have become one of the key factors for many college students to choose the path of entrepreneurship. It is also worth noting that in practice, a comprehensive consideration of various factors is needed to assess the extent to which they have a positive impact on entrepreneurial intentions, and these factors may exhibit different expressions in different contexts.

REFERENCES

1. Ao, J., & Liu, Z. (2014). What impact entrepreneurial intention? Cultural, environmental, and educational factors. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 1(3), 224-239.
2. Abbasianchavari, A., & Moritz, A. (2021). The impact of role models on entrepreneurial intentions and behavior: a review of the literature. *Management Review Quarterly*, 71, 1-40.
3. Alam, M. Z., Kousar, S., & Rehman, C. A. (2019). Role of entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial intentions and behaviour: theory of planned behaviour extension on engineering students in Pakistan. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), 1-20.
4. A Liñán, F. and Chen, Y.W. (2009). "Development and cross-cultural application of a specific instrument to measure entrepreneurial intentions", *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, Vol. 33 No. 3, 593–617.
5. Ali, S., Alshiqi, S., Ferasso, M., Sahiti, A., & Bekteshi, X. (2023). Entrepreneurial intentions and perceived advantages by Eastern students. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 10(4), 63-75
6. Barba-Sánchez, V., Mitre-Aranda, M., & del Brío-González, J. (2022). The entrepreneurial intention of university students: An environmental perspective. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(2), 100184. doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100184
7. Bazkiaei, H. A., Heng, L. H., Khan, N. U., Saufi, R. B. A., & Kasim, R. S. R. (2020). Do entrepreneurial education and big-five personality traits predict entrepreneurial intention among universities students?. *Cogent business & management*, 7(1), 1801217. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1801217>
8. Bjørnø, A. M. (2018). Career ambitions, expectations and skills among music students at higher education institutions-A literature review and empirical study (Master's thesis, NTNU).
9. Bu, Y.Q. (2018). Current situation and countermeasures of college students' entrepreneurship from the perspective of urban and application. *Literature Education*, (04), 107-109. doi:10.16692/j.cnki.wxjyx.2018.04.050.

10. Chen, Q.Y. & Yang ,H.X.(2022). An empirical study on personality traits, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention of post-00s college students. *Educational observation*, 22-27. Doi: 10.16070 / j.carol carroll nki cn45-1388 / g4s 2022.29.029.
11. Chen,L.B., L, T., W, X.H. & L, C.C. (2024). How family socioeconomic status affects college students' entrepreneurial competence: the mediating role of social support. *Educational Development Research*,(03), 55-64. doi:10.14121/j.cnki.1008-3855.2024.03.013.
12. Citrawandi, N., & Susanto, P. (2020, November). Analysis of Education of Entrepreneurship, Curriculum Implementation, and Lecturer Competence Towards the Interest of Entrepreneurship of Students in Jambi Province. In *The Fifth Padang International Conference On Economics Education, Economics, Business and Management, Accounting and Entrepreneurship (PICEEBA-5 2020)* (pp. 422-429).
13. Chen, S. C., Hsiao, H. C., Chang, J. C., Chou, C. M., Chen, C. P., & Shen, C. H. (2015). Can the entrepreneurship course improve the entrepreneurial intentions of students?. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 11, 557-569.
14. Farooq, M. S. (2018). Modelling the significance of social support and entrepreneurial skills for determining entrepreneurial behaviour of individuals: A structural equation modelling approach. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 14(3), 242-266.
15. Farooq, M.S., Jaafar, N., Ayupp, K., Salam, M., Mughal, Y.H., Azam, F. and Sajid, A. (2016), "Impact of entrepreneurial skills and family occupation on entrepreneurial intentions", *ScienceInternational*, Vol. 28 No. 3, pp. 3145-3148.
16. Fu ,X. (2016). Research on social support for college students' entrepreneurship. *Chinese market* (21), 138-139. The doi: 10.13939 / j.carol carroll nki ZGSC. 2016.21.138.
17. Fragooso, R., Rocha-Junior, W., & Xavier, A. (2020). Determinant factors of entrepreneurial intention among university students in Brazil and Portugal. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 32(1), 33-57.
18. Elshaer, I. A., & Sobaih, A. E. E. (2023). The Impact of Gender on the Link between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Intention: Implications for Sustainable Agriculture. *Agriculture*, 13(2), 454. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13020454>.
19. Gao, Y., & Qin, X. (2022). Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention of Chinese college students: Evidence from a moderated multi-mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1049232. doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1049232.
20. Guo, W.D.(2018). Investigation and analysis of college students' innovation and entrepreneurship ability. *Journal of sichuan institute for nationalities* (4), 100-104. The doi: 10.13934 / j.carol carroll nki/g4.2018.04.017 cn51-1729.
21. Hu, T.(2022). Research on the optimization of innovative talents training system in universities from the Interdisciplinary perspective. *Applied Higher Education Research* (01),49-54.
22. Hong,F.(2021).Research on innovation and entrepreneurship education practice of college music college students. *Employment and Security*(05),77-78. doi:CNKI:SUN:JUYE.0.2021-05-042.
23. Hutasuhut, S. (2018). The roles of entrepreneurship knowledge, EM, family, education, and gender on entrepreneurial intention. *Dinamika Pendidikan*, 13(1), 90-105.

24. Hutagalung, B., Dalimunthe, D. M., Pambudi, R., Hutagalung, A. Q., & Muda, I. (2017). The effect of entrepreneurship education and family environment towards students' entrepreneurial motivation.
25. Hu, Y.Q.(2014) Research on Influencing Factors of college students' entrepreneurial Tendency based on Planned Behavior Theory. *Educational Development Research*,34(9),77-82.
26. Israr, M., & Saleem, M. (2018). Entrepreneurial intentions among university students in Italy. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 8(1), 1-14.
27. Jen, S. H. S. (2019). Understanding and enhancing the development of entrepreneurial motivation in undergraduate music students (Doctoral dissertation, University of Leeds).Retrieved from https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/25414/1/Jen_SS_Music_PhD_2019.pdf
28. Jiang, Y. (2021). Education reform and quality training of music majors from the perspective of entrepreneurial education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 749701. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.749701>
29. Johnson-Helms, S. (2023). *Creating New Career Paths In Music: A Graduate Level Minor Field Curriculum In Music Entrepreneurship For Performers*(Doctoral dissertation, Indiana University).Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/>
30. Khayru, R. K., Nichen, N., Chairunnas, A., Safaruddin, S., & Tahir, M. (2021). Study on the relationship between social support and entrepreneurship intention experienced by adolescents. *Journal of Social Science Studies (JOS3)*, 1(2), 47-51.
31. Langford, C.P.H., Bowsher, J., Maloney, J.P. and Lillis, P.P. (1997), "Social support: a conceptual analysis", *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 95-100.
32. Lei ,J.(2020). Cultivation of teaching practice ability of college Musicology students under the background of innovation and entrepreneurship education. *Theatre House* (23),166-167.
33. Li,S.D. (2022). Exploration on Innovation and entrepreneurship of college students majoring in music. *Art Review* (13), 177-180.
34. Li,Y.F & D,P.P. (2023). Research on comprehensive reform of college Music performance majors under the background of Innovation and Entrepreneurship. *Theoretical Research and Practice of Innovation and Entrepreneurship* (04), 77-80.
35. Li,Y.Q., Bai,X., Mao,Y., & Zeng, Z. (2008). Analysis of the Influence Factors of Students' Entrepreneurial Intentions Based on the TPB Model. *Chinese Soft Science* (5), 122-128.
36. Liu, X., Lin, C., Zhao, G., & Zhao, D. (2019). Research on the effects of entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial EM on college students' entrepreneurial intention. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 869.
37. Liu, Q., Zhao, B.X. & Shi, J.W. (2017). A discussion on the application of social support network theory in college students' entrepreneurship. *Science and Technology Wind* (06), 248+250. doi:10.19392/j.cnki.1671-7341.201706223.
38. Liu,M.M. (2023). Research on the Optimization of Local University Entrepreneurial Education Ecosystem from the perspective of Niche Theory Master's Degree Thesis, Hubei Normal University. Master's <https://link.cnki.net/doi/10.27796/d.cnki.ghbsf.2023.000360> doi: 10.27796 /, dc nki. GHBSF. 2023.000360.

39. Lu, G., Song, Y., & Pan, B. (2021). How university entrepreneurship support affects college students' entrepreneurial intentions: An empirical analysis from China. *Sustainability*, 13(6), 3224. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063224>.
40. Ma, Y., & Han, S. (2023, May). A Survey on Entrepreneurship of Music Students in Hubei Normal University. In *Information and Knowledge Management* (Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 20-30).
41. Maheshwari, G. (2022). Entrepreneurial intentions of university students in Vietnam: Integrated model of social learning, human motivation, and TPB. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(3), 100714.
42. Neneh, B. N. (2022). Entrepreneurial passion and entrepreneurial intention: the role of social support and entrepreneurial EM. *Studies in Higher Education*, 47(3), 587-603.
43. Pruet, M., Shinnar, R., Toney, B., Llopis, F., & Fox, J. (2009). Explaining entrepreneurial intentions of university students: a cross-cultural study. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 15(6), 571-594.
44. Pulka, B.M, Rikwentish, R. Mani. U. A.U & Jossiah, mm. (2015). Variation of attitude among university students towards entrepreneurship education. *Journal of Business administration and Education*, 7 (2), 177-195.
45. Şahin, F., Karadağ, H., & Tuncer, B. (2019). Big five personality traits, entrepreneurial EM and entrepreneurial intention: A configurational approach. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 25(6), 1188-1211.
46. Schwarz, E. J., Wdowiak, M. A., Almer-Jarz, D. A., & Breiteneker, R. J. (2009). The effects of attitudes and perceived environment conditions on students' entrepreneurial intent: An Austrian perspective. *Education+ Training*, 51(4), 272-291.
47. Si, W., Yan, Q., Wang, W., Meng, L., & Zhang, M. (2022). Research on the Influence of Non-Cognitive Ability and Social Support Perception on College Students' Entrepreneurial Intention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(19), 11981.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191911981.
48. Shi, Y., Yuan, T., Bell, R., & Wang, J. (2020). Investigating the relationship between creativity and entrepreneurial intention: the moderating role of creativity in the theory of planned behavior. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1209.
49. Shi, J., & Chen, C. (2022). Status Quo and education of entrepreneurial ability of local college students majoring in music. *Look at History* (2), 0145-0147.
50. Shamsudin, S. F. F. B., Mamun, A. A., Nawi, N. B. C., Nasir, N. A. B. M., & Zakaria, M. N. B. (2017). Factors affecting entrepreneurial intention among the Malaysian university students. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 51(4), 423-431.
51. Snuggs, E., & Jevons, C. (2018). Reconceptualising the scholarship of marketing education- SOME futurescapes. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 26, 180-186.
52. Tao, M., & Hu, W. J. (2018). Research on Personality Traits of successful entrepreneurial college students based on Five-factor personality model: Problems and possibilities. *Journal of hebei agricultural university (agriculture and forestry education edition)* (03), 8 to 11. Doi: 10.13320/j.carol carroll nki jauhe. 2018.0056.
53. Toscher, B. (2019). Entrepreneurial learning in arts entrepreneurship education: A conceptual framework. *Artivate*, 8(1), 3-22.
54. Tsaknis, P. A., Sahinidis, A. G., Tsakni, G. J., Vassiliou, E. V., Kavagia, C. A., Giovanis, A. N., & Stavroulakis, D. (2022). Personality effect on students' entrepreneurial

- intention: The mediating effect of the theory of planned behavior. *Corporate & Business Strategy Review*, 3(2), 86–95.
55. Uchino, B. (2004), *Social Support and Physical Health: Understanding the Health Consequences of Relationships*, Yale University Press, New Haven, CT.
 56. Valdez-Juárez, L. E., & Pérez-de-Lema, D. G. (2023). Creativity and the family environment, facilitators of EM for entrepreneurial intentions in university students: Case ITSON Mexico. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 21(1), 100764.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100764.
 57. Wang, D., Wang, L., & Chen, L. (2018). Unlocking the influence of family business exposure on entrepreneurial intentions. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 14, 951-974.
 58. Wills, T.A. (1985), “Supportive functions of interpersonal relationships”, in Cohen, S. and Syme, L.(Eds), *Social Support and Health*, Academic Press, Orlando, FL, pp. 61-82.
 59. Wills, T.A. (1991), “Social support and interpersonal relationships”, in Clark, M. (Ed.), *Prosocial Behavior, Review of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 12, Sage Publications, Inc., Thousand Oaks, CA, pp. 265-289.
 60. Wu, S., & Wu, L. (2008). The impact of higher education on entrepreneurial intentions of university students in China. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 15(4), 752-774.
 61. Yao, T.Y.(2019). Project-driven exploration and practice of college students' innovation and entrepreneurship education. *The Fatherland* (13),189-190.
 62. Yang, Y.S., Zeng, Y.Q., & Shao, X.(2023). The willingness and influencing factors of Hong Kong and Macao University students to start businesses in the Bay Area from the perspective of TPB. *Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education* (05),21-27.
 63. Zhan, Y.(2019). Status Quo of college students' entrepreneurship and quality improvement of mass creation in art universities: A case study of Sichuan Film and Television Institute. *Time Report* (05),240-241.
 64. Zhao, H., & Seibert, S. E. (2006). The big five personality dimensions and entrepreneurial status: a meta-analytical review. *Journal of applied psychology*, 91(2), 259.